

Phase stability, Electronic and Optical Behavior of PbS, PbSe and PbTe Compounds

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ABSTRACT

Ab initio calculations based on density functional theory using the full potential linearized augmented plane wave method (**FP-LAPW**) have been carried out to find the structural stability of different crystallographic phases, the electronic and optical properties of **PbS**, **PbSe** and **PbTe** compounds. The zinc blende (**B3**), rock salt (**B1**) and CsCl (**B2**). crystal structures are considered and the exchange and correlation potential is treated by the generalized-gradient approximation using the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof parameterization. Moreover, the modified Becke-Johnson (**mBJ**) scheme is also applied to optimize the corresponding potential for the band structure calculations. Results show that the rock salt phase is the stable structure in the ground state adopted by **PbS**, **PbTe** and **PbSe** compounds. Moreover, the band structure calculations reveal a semiconductor behavior for all the compounds. The dielectric function, reflectivity, Refractive index and absorption coefficient are calculated to investigate the optical properties.

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1. Introduction

During the past decades, the lead chalcogenides, **PbX** (**X = S, Se and Te**) have been a subject of a great amount of theoretical and experimental studies, motivated by their importance infrared technology, and more recently, because of their utility in laser technology and as thermoelectric materials. The **PbX** compounds are narrow direct gap semiconductors (group IV–VI), which crystallize at ambient conditions in the cubic NaCl structure. The lead salts exhibit properties which are unusual, relative to other semiconductors. Compared for example, with the usual III–V compounds, these IV–VI chalcogens present non-typical electronic and transport properties, such as higher carrier mobilities, higher dielectric constants, narrow band gaps and positive temperature coefficients (Cowley 1965; Dalven 1973; Murase 1980) [1]. These properties make them potential candidates for different technological applications. They have been used in thermos-electronic, optoelectronic or spintronic devices, especially in long

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wavelength imaging (Hummer et al 2007) [2], infrared diode lasers (Preier 1979) and in thermos-photovoltaic energy converters (Zogg et al 1994) [3]. The semiconductors **PbS, PbSe and PbTe** show a small direct gap at the L point of the Brillouin zone. In contrast to most of the semiconductors, this gap decreases with hydrostatic pressure (Andreev 1968; Besson et al 1968; Martinez 1973) and increases with temperature (Tauber et al 1966; Andreev 1968; Martinez 1973) [4]. Polycrystalline evaporated films of **PbS, PbSe, and PbTe** have been used for many years as infrared photoconductive detectors. Despite their widespread use, the mechanism of sensitivity is poorly understood. The structure, electrical properties, and recombination processes of the films have never been resolved satisfactorily. The study of the epitaxial films was originally undertaken to shed some light on these various processes. It became apparent from the outset, that the properties of the photoconductive and epitaxial films are radically different. Among these differences is that no measurable photoconductivity has been observed in any epitaxial film grown to date. However, no attempt has been made to sensitize the films, so that this does not preclude the possibility that sensitive infrared photodetectors could be produced by epitaxial techniques. [5]. In this paper we studied **the structural, electronic, optical, and optical properties** of these compounds. Moreover, we relied on the full-potential linearized augmented plane wave (**FP-LAPW**) as implemented by Wien2K code. In section 2, we briefly describe the computational method used in the present work. Results will be presented in section 3. Finally, a brief summary and our conclusions are given in the “Conclusions” section 4.

1. Computational Method

The calculations were performed using the full-potential linearized augmented plane wave (FP-LAPW) method [6] within the framework of the DFT [6, 7] as implemented in the WIEN2K code [7], which is one of the most efficient methods of simulating and calculating the ground state properties of crystalline materials [8]. The exchange-correlation potential for the structural properties was calculated by the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) based on Perdew et al. [9], while for the electronic properties, the Becke-Johnson (mBj) scheme [10] was applied. In the FP-LAPW method, the wave function, charge density and potential are expanded differently in two regions of the unit cell. Inside the non-overlapping spheres around each atom of radius R_{MT} (muffin-tin radius), spherical harmonic expansion is used and in the remaining space of the unit cell, a plane wave basis set is chosen. The convergence parameter, $R_{MT}k_{max}$ which controls the size of the basis sets in these calculations, was set to 8. R_{MT} denotes the smallest atomic sphere radius and k_{max} gives the magnitude of the largest k vector in the plane wave expansion. The charge density was Fourier expanded up to $G_{max} = 14$ (Ryd) $^{1/2}$ and the maximum l quantum number for the wave function expansion inside the atomic spheres was confined to $l_{max} = 10$. The muffin-tin radius was assumed to be **2.0, 2.0, 2.2 and 2.0** atomic units (a.u.) for the **Pb, S, Se and Te** atoms, respectively. A mesh of 47 special k -points for these binary compounds was taken in the irreducible wedge of the Brillouin zone. Both the plane wave cut-off and the number of k -points were varied to ensure total energy convergence.

2. Results and discussion

3.1. Structural Properties

The first step of our calculations was to study the phase stability of the **PbS, PbSe and PbTe** compounds.

It was demonstrated theoretically that for binary solids there extends a dense spectrum of as yet undiscovered polymorphs lying in an energetically narrow range above their phase ground states, with very small total energy differences between different polymorphs [11–15]. The diverse range of materials considered indicates that this is likely to be a general phenomenon. Motivated by these findings, several possible structural phases including the rock-salt (B1), cesium chloride (B2), zinc blende (B3). We show the calculated total energies per formula unit at different values of the unit cell volume for all the phases studied in this work. Our GGA calculations show that the **rocksalt (NaCl)** structure is the ground stable phase adopted by **PbSe, PbTe and PbS** compounds with the lowest calculated total energy at zero pressure. our results are in accordance with several experimental studies [15– 19] and previous theoretical results whose calculations are based on the GGA approximation [20,21]. In the next step, we calculated the structural parameters for the alloy, the parameter lattice a , the modulus of compressibility B , and its derivative B' in the 3 phases. The values obtained are presented in Table 1, which also contains experimental and theoretical data as available in the literature [20,21]. The reason behind that is the use of the WC-GGA approximation. For phases studied only via theoretical calculation methods, our results are generally in agreement with other prior studies [20,21].

Fig.1 Total energy as a function of the volume calculated in the zinc blende phases (B3), NaCl (B1) and CsCl (B2) for the PbS, PbTe and PbSe compounds.

Table 1. Lattice constant a , bulk modulus B , pressure derivative of bulk modulus B' and elastic constant parameters of **PbS**, **PbSe** and **PbTe** compared with the experimental data and other theoretical works.

	Present Work			Other Works	
	LDA	GGA	Experimental	LDA	GGA
PbS					
$a(A^0)$	5.765	5.992	5.929 ^a , 5.936 ^{c,d} , 5.940 ^f	5.860 ^b , 5.906 ^e	
B	62.986			6.012 ^{b, g}	
B'	54.982			64.8 ^b	53.3 ^b
	4.765	4.982		-	-
PbSe					
$a(A^0)$			6.117 ^a , 6.124 ^{c,d} , 6.130 ^f	6.053 ^b ,	6.098 ^e
B	6.087	6.2317		6.196 ^b	
B'	57.653	49.876		58.3 ^b , 60.8 ^e	120.8 ^b
	3.873	3.985		-	-
PbTe					
$a(A^0)$	6.224	6.432	6.462 ^{a,c} , 6.460 ^f	6.37 ^b , 6.44 ^e	6.56 ^b ,
B	48.996	38.407		6.57 ^g	
B'	4.124	4.123		51.4 ^b	41.4 ^b
				-	-

^a[22], ^b[23]; ^c [24]; ^d [25]; ^e [26]; ^f [27] and ^g [28]

3.2. Electronic properties:

We have studied in this part the electronic properties of the binary compounds. In solid physics, energy bands give the possible energies of an electron in function of the wave vector k . From the dispersion equation $E(k)$ which represents a very important property in the case of semiconductors, these electronic properties include band structures, gap energies (E_g), state densities. In our study, we calculated the energy bands of binary compounds PbTe, PbSe and PbS along the lines of high symmetry of the first Brillouin zone, in using both approximations (**GGA**) and (**mbj**). The band structures obtained for each compound by the use of two approximations have almost the same pace, this is why only the curves obtained using the (GGA) are shown in **Fig (2) and (3)**. Therefore, **PbSe, PbS and PbTe** have an indirect gap in the direction (L-L)

Fig2. Band structure of the PbS, PbTe and PbSe compounds in the NaCl structure using the WC-GGA in NaCl phase.

Fig3. Band structure of the PbS, PbTe and PbSe compounds in the NaCl structure using the mbj in NaCl phase

We calculated the gap energy value of this compounds. The results obtained are shown in **Table 2**. The gaps obtained by the mBJ approximation, are in agreement with the experimentally calculated gaps for the binary compounds PbS, PbTe and PbSe.

Table 2. Energy band gaps (L → L) in (eV) of **PbS, PbSe and PbTe** compounds in the NaCl structure using the mbj in NaCl phase

	Present work			
	GGA	mBj	Experimental	Other works
PbS	0.187 0.765		0.290 ^a	0.380 ^b , 0.448 ^c , 0.074 ^d
PbSe	0.021 0.878		0.17 ^a	0.340 ^b , 0.318 ^c , 0.022 ^d , 0.121 ^f
PbTe	0.1987 1.321		0.19 ^e	0.737 ^b , 0.643 ^c , 0.16 ^f

a [23]; b [24]; c [25]; e[26]

3.3 Optical properties :

The optical properties of the material can be described by means of the complex dielectric function. The latter linearly relates the electric field $\mathbf{E}(\omega)$ to the electric induction $\mathbf{D}(\omega)$ by means of the following equation [29].

$$\mathbf{D}(\omega) = \epsilon(\omega) \mathbf{E}(\omega) \quad (1)$$

For a dynamic field, $\varepsilon(\omega)$ corresponds to a complex function of the frequency of the electric field [52-55]:

$$\varepsilon(\omega) = \varepsilon_1(\omega) + i\varepsilon_2(\omega) \quad (2)$$

$\varepsilon_1(\omega)$: represents the real part of the polarization of the medium.

It is possible to extract the real and imaginary parts of the dielectric function using the kramers-kronig relations [30, 31]:

$$\varepsilon_1(\omega) = 1 + \frac{2}{\pi} P \int_0^\infty \frac{\omega' \varepsilon_2(\omega')}{(\omega'^2 - \omega^2)} d\omega' \quad (3)$$

$$\varepsilon_2(\omega) = -\frac{2\omega}{\pi} P \int_0^\infty \frac{\varepsilon_1(\omega') - 1}{(\omega'^2 - \omega^2)} d\omega' \quad (4)$$

P: being the principal value of the Cauchy integral. The complex refractive index, linked to the dielectric function (ε) will be to describe the medium; it is written on the format:

$$\mathbf{N}(\omega) = \mathbf{n}(\omega) + i\mathbf{K}(\omega). \text{ Ces deux grandeurs sont liées avec cette relation : } \varepsilon = \mathbf{N}^2.$$

The real and imaginary parts of the dielectric function are related to the refractive index (n) and the extinction coefficient (K) according to these formulas:

$$\varepsilon_1(\omega) = n^2 - K^2 \quad (5)$$

$$\varepsilon_2(\omega) = 2nK \quad (6)$$

The real refractive index n and the extinction coefficient K (losses) can be given by means of the following two relations [32, 33]:

$$n(\omega) = \left\{ \frac{\varepsilon_1(\omega)}{2} + \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon_1^2(\omega) + \varepsilon_2^2(\omega)}{2}} \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (7)$$

$$K(\omega) = \left\{ \frac{\sqrt{\varepsilon_1^2(\omega) + \varepsilon_2^2(\omega)}}{2} - \frac{\varepsilon_1(\omega)}{2} \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (8)$$

Reflectivity is an important optical function calculated from the indices of refraction $n(\omega)$ and extinction $K(\omega)$:

$$\mathbf{R}(\omega) = [(1 - n)^2 + K^2] / [(1 + n)^2 + K^2] \quad (9)$$

For low frequencies ($\omega = 0$) relation (7) becomes:

$$\mathbf{n}(0) = \varepsilon^{1/2}(0) \quad (10)$$

Figure 7 illustrates the ϵ_1 variation as an energy function for the binary compounds **PbS**, **PbTe** and **PbSe**. Overall, we can observe that the spectra almost have the exact same appearance, bar some minor differences. We also note that for all these compounds, **the function $\epsilon_1(0)$ is invalid** when it comes to the following values of energy: 21.966 (**PbS**), 17.990 (**PbSe**), 13.228 (**PbTe**). Furthermore, it ought to be mentioned that at these energy values, the dispersion is zero. Therefore, the absorption is at maximum level. The calculation results of **the imaginary part $\epsilon_2(\omega)$** of the dielectric function in the range of energy from 0 to 25 eV for these binary compounds are illustrated in **Figure (4-8)**. The analysis of these spectra shows that the behavior of **$\epsilon_2(\omega)$** is almost similar for all four compounds, and the first critical points of the dielectric function that corresponds to the fundamental absorption thresholds start at about 3.14, 2.19, 1.15 and 1.07 eV for **PbS**, **PbSe** and **PbTe** respectively. The origin of these points is due to the optical transition between the highest valence band and the lowest conduction band. Thus, we notice next to the fundamental peak the main peaks that reflect the maximum absorption, are located **6.12, 5.04, 5.35 and 4.45 eV**. These peaks characterize the transitions (Lv-Lc). From the calculated results of the real part of the dielectric function, we have determined the static dielectric constant $\epsilon_1(0)$ which is a larger quantity and given by the lower limit of the energy of $\epsilon(\omega)$. The values of the static dielectric constant $\epsilon_1(0)$ and of the static refractive index $n(0)$ obtained for the compounds PbX) **in table 3**. The comparison with the theoretical data available in the literature was also made. Note that the calculated values of **$\epsilon_1(0)$ and $n(0)$** are in good agreement with other theoretical works. The evolution of these spectra shows that the values of the refractive index of the PbS, PbTe PbSe compounds reach a maximum value at the energies **5.34, 4.86, 5.18, 2.63 eV**, respectively.

Fig.4. Variation of the real part of the dielectric function according to the energy for compounds PbS, PbSe and PbTe.

Fig5. Variation of the imaginary part of the dielectric function as a function of energy for the compounds PbS, PbSe and PbTe.

Fig 6. Refractive index variation as a function of energy for compounds PbS, PbSe and PbTe.

The variation of the absorption coefficient, as a function of energy for the binary compounds PbS, PbSe and PbTe_{xx} between 0 and 40 eV is shown in **Figure 7**. We note that the fundamental absorption thresholds start at around 0.050, 0.582 and 0.617 eV for PbS, PbSe and PbTe respectively. The curves demonstrate the maximal values at energy levels 2.879 eV (**PbS**), 3.761 eV (**PbSe**) and 2.302 eV (**PbTe**).

The evolution of the reflectivity of studied compounds is shown in Figure 11 from the spectra of the value of reflectivity in the energy interval [0-40] eV. The curves indicate a maximum of 35% (**PbSe**), 38% (**PbS**) and 42% (**PbTe**). These results indicate that our materials are a good candidate for utilization in the infrared domain.

Table 3: Values of the static dielectric constants $\epsilon_1(0)$ and the refractive index $n(\omega)$ for PbS, PbSe and PbTe.

Compounds	$\epsilon_1(0)$	$n(0)$
	GGA	GGA
PbS	$\epsilon_1=17,719$	$n(0)=4.173$
PbSe	$\epsilon_1=15.081$	$n(0)=3.244$
PbTe	$\epsilon_1=23.359$	$n(0)=4.67$

Fig 9. Refractive index variation as a function of energy for compounds PbS, PbSe and PbTe.

1. Conclusion:

Employing the FP-LAPW method within the DFT in the framework of GGA and mBJ, we have studied

the phase stability, pressure-induced phase transition, structural and electronic properties of the PbS, PbSe and PbTe compounds. A summary of our results is as follows: at zero pressure, the Rocksalt NaCl phase is found to be the most stable for PbSe, PbS and PbTe compounds. The calculated structural properties in our work are in good agreement with the available data and our band gaps, using GGA are lower than the experimental ones. The band gaps calculated with the mBJ functional are much better than the GGA and are closer to the experimental results .

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